

Linguistic Principles of Creating a Database of Uzbek English Linguistic Terms

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Abstract. *In world linguistics, there is always a question of creating terms became relevant and this issue has not lost its importance even today. In this article, linguistic creation principles of a database of English and Uzbek linguistic terms are defined. Every foreign language learner in the process of learning any languages uses dictionaries. Each dictionary belongs to some fields such as linguistic, economic, medical and so on. Additionally, the article is devoted to investigate historical development of lexicography and dictionaries in the English and Uzbek languages. The article describes development of both English and Uzbek language lexicography included into dictionaries. Some methods like observation and comparison is used to reveal differences and similarities of terminology and dictionaries. Much attention is paid to the classification of dictionaries and the characteristics of the main types of dictionaries in English and Uzbek. The structure of dictionaries and entries are analyzed on the material of dictionaries in both languages. English and Uzbek lexicography comparison is carried out at the end of the article. There are also comments on the need for online dictionaries in the Uzbek language. The issue of creating a terminological database (TBD) and the creation of Uzbek online dictionary are illustrated as an urgent task today.*

Key words: *terminology, term, atama, lexicography, dictionary, online dictionary, electronic dictionary, paper dictionary.*

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, governing study of linguistics is terminology because it consists of a set of terms, symbols and names belonging to in any language. Terminology is multiple discipline that it borrows its basic tools and concepts from a number of disciplines such as logic, ontology, linguistics, information science and others. According to Sager, the theory of terminology can be revealed as having three distinctive dimensions like the cognitive, the linguistic, and the communicative dimension.¹

The aspects of “science-specific” grammar, which means the language of science promotes very accurate and unambiguous expressions and terms that leads to a higher rate of repetitive expressions, to the frequent utilization of relative pronouns or adverbials, for example, the technical vocabulary, mostly based on Greek as well as Latin terms with lots of compounds that can be long, imposing abbreviations in use and others. That all were described by David Crystal and according to him, the development of science and new discoveries urge the continuous renewal and enrichment of new vocabulary.²

¹ Sager J. C. A practical course in terminology processing //A Practical Course in Terminology Processing. – 1990. – P. 86-87.

² Nagy I. K. et al. English for special purposes: Specialized languages and problems of terminology //Acta Universitatis Sapientiae, Philologica. – 2014. – №. 2. – P. 261-273.

As well as in her book entitled “Terminology”, M. Teresa Cabré differentiates special language from artificial languages and according to her, special languages exist a number of features in common with the comparison of general language.³ Technical terms are characterized by apparentness and accuracy. These terms are subject to a higher degree of normalization and standardization. They are used in specific contexts as well as they are listed in specialized dictionaries and glossaries. “Technical terms denote to those lexical units exclusively utilized by a given knowledge community in a specific domain also well known as terminology or subject specific terms.”

Thus, the term of “Academic and Professional languages” was coined by Alcaraz, refers to the sort of language used by specific knowledge communities or group of professionals, for instance, chemists, lawyers, physicians and others that share the same values and institutions which utilize similar genres and terminology to communicate. Additionally, this term is used in specialized communication, an academic or professional setting and characterized as having a restricted number of users in order to avoid any controversy.⁴

Moreover, in Uzbek language have thoughts on specific substantiation of linguistic terms were offered by Abduratif Fitrat as well as Mashrik Yunusov (Elbek). The idea of need to work a bit harder and help each other to define every rules of our language and put their terms on the field, was suggested by Fitrat and he wrote textbooks under the name of “Nahv” and “Sarf”. “Sarf” is dedicated to phonetics and morphology while “Nahv” interprets terms based on speech, parts of speech, types of speech, introductory words and their explanations.⁵

In Elbek’s research also the study of linguistic terms are reflected. Particularly, in of phonetics and morphemes of linguistics, he explains specific and theoretical ideas in these fields of linguistics. He uses the term vowel regarding the sounds of speech and letters in phonetics as well as at the same time, he interpreted the term of words and adjectives.⁶

Recently, in the research of L.V Reshetova, A. Khodzhiev, I.M Yakubov, A.N Rajabov, S.T Mustafaeva, D.I Khodjaeva, I.R Ermatov reflect the ideas on the issue of linguistic terms. L.V. Reshetova has studied the terms related to Direct Grammar of Uzbek language, which the main focus is on the analysis of Uzbek grammatical terminology. Furthermore, A. Khodzhiev studied the criteria for the selection of terms as well as the state of linguistic terminology of Uzbek language. Also, D.I. Khodjaeva conducted a comparative as well as comparative lexicographical analysis of linguistic terms on the basis of materials of explanatory dictionaries of three languages such as English, Russian and Uzbek.

METHODOLOGY

In this paper some methods are used such as comparison and observation so as to investigate the research paper. Comparison is used in order to compare formation of linguistic terms in English and Uzbek as well as the reason of usage observation is to observe other researchers’ works and data related to linguistic principles of creating linguistic terms in both languages.

Linguistic principles

Structuralism is a term used in linguistics denoting to a theoretical approach to the analysis of language, which describes linguistic items of structures. The father of structuralism is Ferdinand de Saussure as well as in 1916, his “Course in General linguistics” was published, where the main ideas of structuralism were formulated. He formulated that several principles of linguistic analysis that have become the tenets of modern linguistics. Followings are these principles with short explanations:

³ Cabré M. T. Terminology: Theory, methods, and applications. – John Benjamins Publishing, 1999. – P. 59-61

⁴ Nagy I. K. et al. English for special purposes: Specialized languages and problems of terminology //Acta Universitatis Sapientiae, Philologica. – 2014. – №. 2. – P. 261-273.

⁵ Abdurauf Fitrat. Selected works Volume IV: textbooks and manuals, scientific articles and research. - Tashkent: Manaviyat, 2006. - P. 140-213

⁶ Elbek Selected works // Foreword by the author: H. Uzoqov; Responsible editor: Sh. Salimova. - Tashkent: Sharq, 1999. - P. 275-283

Linguistics is descriptive, not prescriptive: It means that linguists illustrate the rules and facts of language exactly as they find out them without making any judgements. The main task of linguists is to describe the way people speak and write, not to tell them how they should use the language.

Synchronic and diachronic description of language: Both synchronic and diachronic principles can be applied to the study of language. Diachronic linguistics is the study of languages from the viewpoint their historical development while synchronic studies languages at a single point of time. Both ways of illustrating languages are crucial.

Paradigmatic and syntagmatic relations of linguistic units: Two different kinds of linguistic units enters into relations, which identify it in language system. It enters into paradigmatic relations with other elements of similar level, which can be used in the same context. For instance, in the phrase “a...of milk”, the omitted element could be glass, jar, mug, bottle. All these countable nouns stand in paradigmatic relationship.

Syntagmatic relations with the other element of the same level that it occurs and make its context. Syntagmatic relations for “a glass of milk” would be between glass and a, of, and milk.⁷

Terminology

Using the method of observation, it is found that “the term” has various meanings such as according to Merriam Webster dictionary it means “a word or expression that has an extended meaning in some uses or is peculiar to a science, art, profession, or subject”⁸.

As well as meaning of “terminology” is “the scientific field pertaining to the study of relations between concepts and their designations (terms, names and symbols) and the formulation of principles as well as methods governing these relations in any given subject field. Moreover, the task of collecting, processing, managing as well as presenting terminological data in one or more languages”.⁹

In Uzbek language has the concept “Atama” that means a word or phrase that is a clear and stable expression of a specific concept in specific field of science, technology, or profession.¹⁰

The terms are “the properties of the parts of speech: the adjective, verb, adverbs are not contained in terminological relations independently, but through the medium of a noun” according to B. N. Golovin. The terms represent the official names of the special notions.¹¹

The terminological dictionaries are created so far have scope, purpose, and function according to the method of description. Terminologist Z.I.Komarova classifies terminological dictionaries based on eleven aspects:

1. According to the number of languages represented (monolingual, bilingual, multilingual);
2. According to the main function (interpretation, translation, system);
3. By the proposed field or field of science (general, sectoral, narrow sectoral, multidisciplinary);
4. According to the special task (conceptual, frequency, left, reading);
5. According to the principle of existence and semantization of terms (encyclopedic, explanatory, non-explanatory, etc.);
6. By vocabulary (perfect, average, concise);
7. According to the purpose (for information censorship specialists, researchers, practitioners, students, colleges, students, etc.);
8. Widely used (human dictionaries, computer-oriented dictionaries);

⁷ De Saussure F. Course in general linguistics. – 1959. – P. 87-96.

⁸ Dictionary M. W. Merriam-webster //On-line at <http://www.mw.com/home.htm>. – 2002. – №. 2.

⁹ Dictionary M. W. Merriam-webster //On-line at <http://www.mw.com/home.htm>. – 2002. – №. 2.

¹⁰ Madvaliyev A., Mahkamov N., Mahmudov N. O ‘zbek tilining izohli lug ‘ati. – 2006. P. 73

¹¹ Golovin B. N., Kobrin R. Y. Lingvisticheskie osnovy ucheniya o terminakh //Moskva: Vysshaya shkola. – 1987. – P. 56.

9. According to the placement of terms (alphabetical, alphabetic, changing, ideographic left frequency, hierarchical);
10. According to the norm of the uzus (normative, standardized);
11. On the modernity of the term (new, in use, historical).¹²

The formation of eastern lexicography comes back to ancient millennia and it is true that Mahmud Kashgari's work "Devonu lug'otit turk", that laid the foundation for the creating of modern relative Turkic languages, including Uzbek lexicography. The dictionary was created to present the vocabulary of the Turkic languages to the Arabs. It states that modern relative languages, including Uzbek, continue to be used to a certain extent in the lexical treasury and terminological lexicon have an important place in the lexical units of the ancient Turkic language, which is completely obsolete today.

In Uzbek language, Nazir Turakulov's "Political and Economic Dictionary of the Russian-Uzbek Language", published in 1922 was the first terminological dictionary in the history of Uzbek lexicography. It had a special place in Uzbek lexicography as the first terminological dictionary, even though this dictionary was the first lexicographical work devoted to the translation of political and economic terms.¹³

Creating explanatory terminological dictionaries that cover the terms of each field as fully as possible, define the terms that correctly, fully and clearly reflect the essence of the phenomenon in these fields is one of the first tasks of specialists. For this purpose, for the first time, an explanatory dictionary of linguistic terms of the Uzbek language by A. Hojiyev was compiled and published by the "Teacher" publishing house in 1985.¹⁴

During the years of independence, many types of terminological dictionaries on science and other fields were created. In particular, dictionaries have been created in different fields of engineering, medicine, agriculture, physics, chemistry, biology, geography, linguistics. Moreover, the terminological dictionaries are created so far have been concise in size and have served for educational purposes. In the history of Uzbek terminology to date, in more than 50 different branches and fields of science and technology have been created more than 250 terminological dictionaries.¹⁵

Linguistic terms began to be studied comparatively during the years of independence. I.M. Yakubov conducted the analysis of linguistic terms in Russian and Uzbek in 1991. This dissertation for the first time analyzes the effect on Russian linguistic terms on the formation and improvement of Uzbek linguistic terminology.¹⁶ Another comparative study of linguistic terms was conducted in research of A.N. Rajabov as well as in this dissertation the study of linguistic terms in Uzbek and Russian languages is studied and analyzed materials from linguistic terminology scientific collections, monographs, scientific researches, textbooks, manuals, terminological dictionaries and other sources published in Uzbek, Russian and other languages from 1970 to 1992.¹⁷

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

In linguistics of both Uzbek and English languages is interpreted that there are three types of terminological dictionaries: monolingual, bilingual and multilingual. According to some scholars, the division of dictionaries into types occurs for different of reasons: the purpose of the dictionary, its size, how words are placed in it, the object of description, and so on:

¹² Komarova Z. I. Semantic structure of a special word and its lexicographic description //Sverdlovsk: Publishing House of the Ural University. – 1991. – P. 18.

¹³ A. Pardayev, D.B. Urinbayeva, D.A. Islamova. O'zbek terminologiyasi (o'quv qo'llanma) // Samarqand – 2020 – P. 217

¹⁴ Azim Hojiyev. Tilshunoslik terminlarining izohli lug'ati // Toshkent: O'qituvchi. – 1985 – P.3

¹⁵ Madvaliev A. (2008). Term – terminological dictionary - annotated dictionary // Uzbek language and literature. – Tashkent. – P. 59.

¹⁶ Yakubov I.M. Analysis of the equivalence of the linguistic terms of the Russian and Uzbek languages .: Author's abstract. diss. ... Cand. philol. sciences. - Tashkent, 1991 .- P.19

¹⁷ Ражабов А.Н. Вопросы узбекской лингвистической терминологии в сопоставлении с русской.: Автореф. дисс. ...канд. филол. наук. – Ташкент, 1993. – P.20.

Terms according to the amount of languages given					
Monolingual		Bilingual		Multilingual	
Descriptive	Word	Descriptive	Unexplained	Descriptive	Unexplained
According to the placement of the terms					
In Alphabetical order		Mixed (Alphabetical)		Ideographic	
According to the field or science presented					
Sectoral		Mono-sectoral		Multi-sectoral	
According to the purpose and function					
Normative	Training	Informant	Inventory	Illustrative	
According to the method of description					
Descriptive	Encyclopedic	Mixed (brief commentary and encyclopedic description)		Descriptive translation	
The form of the dictionary					
Paper dictionaries		Online dictionaries (only in English)		Electronic dictionaries	
On the modernity of the term					
In use		New		Historical	

Moreover, in the branch of the book “Modern Uzbek literary language”, scholars such as A. Khodzhiyev and A. Akhmedov recommend classifying dictionaries from three perspectives¹⁸:

1. In terms of size:										
a) General dictionaries			b) Special dictionaries							
According to the size of the general dictionaries:			Depending on what purpose the dictionary of special dictionaries is limited:							
a1. Full size	a2. medium	a3. small	b1. lexical layers	b2. lexically selected	b3. terminological					
			b1. synonymous, homonymic, antonymous, compound word, coupling word, taboo-euphemism, phraseological unit, assimilated word dictionaries							
2. In terms of the way the dictionary is given:										
alphabetical order		thematic		mobile						
3. In terms of purpose:										
Translation	definition	historic	etymological	dialectological	comparative	reversal	Orthographic (spelling)	Ortho epic	morpheme	frequent

Initially, paper dictionaries are also known as a print(ed) dictionaries or a book dictionary. A paper dictionary is better, because of its physical form. When you look for a word in the dictionary, you can see the written meaning. Additionally, the meaning of the word lasts longer in your mind if you search it in a paper dictionary. Another big benefit of paper dictionary is that you always come across many different words and pictures while looking for a specific word.

¹⁸ Jamolxonov H. Hozirgi o ‘zbek adabiy tili //Toshkent: O ‘qituvchi. – 2005. – P. 228-231

Electronic dictionary is a dictionary which data exists in digital form and can be accessed through a number of different media. Most of electronic dictionaries are, in effect, print dictionaries made available in digital form: the content is identical, but the electronic editions provide users with more powerful search functions.

The study of online and electronic lexicography began at the same time when computers became a tool for dictionaries. In the book of “The Oxford History of English Lexicography” by Hilary Nesi (Coventry University) is written a detailed review about the history of electronic dictionaries.¹⁹ Also, some researchers made a great contribution to the development of such kind of dictionaries like M. V. Makarych, Yu. B. Popova, M. O. Shved. In the book of M. V. Makarych, “Electronic Lexicography: Traditional and Modern Approaches” is shown a way of creating a database on the example of multilingual English – Belarusian-Russian dictionary.²⁰ But, in Uzbek, there is no any online dictionaries while in English it exists.

The database categorization truly depends on an author’s preference. However, common ways are:

1. Word (transcript) + picture (if applicable) + part of a speech.
2. Meaning.
3. Etymology (optional).
4. Usage.
5. Related words.

Here is below an example of a word “controversial” taken from cambridge.com online English dictionary:

1. Word (transcript): controversial, UK /,kɒn.trəˈvɜː.ʃəl/ US /,kɑːn.trəˈvɜː.ʃəl/, adjective

2. Meaning: causing disagreement or discussion: a controversial issue/decision/speech/figure

3. Usage:

- a) They hold widely divergent opinions on controversial issues like abortion.
- b) Eugenics was the central, and most controversial, part of his social philosophy.
- c) The official censors have excised the controversial sections of the report.
- d) Her controversial speech was punctuated with noisy interjections from the audience.
- e) She has been in the limelight recently, following the release of her controversial new film.

4. Related words (synonyms, antonyms and phrases; nearby words; words from the word):

OTHER WORDS FROM CONTROVERSIAL

Controversially – adverb, controversialist – noun, controversy – noun, controvert – verb.

WORDS RELATED TO CONTROVERSIAL (DEBATE & DISCUSSION)

Agent provocateur, argue for something, argue against something, bargainer, bat, bat around, broker, consult, dialogue, float, honest broker, out bargain, palaver, parley, polarized, polemic, polemical, post-debate, powwow, sophistry.²¹

Here is the example of Uzbek word “bahs” that is taken from Uzbek definition dictionary

1. Word: bahs
2. Meaning: coming to disagreement
3. Usage: a) fikr bahsda qiyomiga yetdi deydi olimlar. Shukurullo. Javohirlar saltanati

¹⁹ Cowie A. P. (ed.). The Oxford History of English Lexicography: Volume I: General-Purpose Dictionaries; Volume II: Specialized Dictionaries. – OUP Oxford, 2008. P.458-478

²⁰ Makarych M. V., Popova Y. B., Shved M. O. Electronic Lexicography: Traditional and Modern Approaches. – 2020. P. 421-427

²¹ <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/controversial>

c) Bahs ketayotganda baqirgan tomon yutkazadi. F. Musajonov. Ximmat

4. Etymology: taken from Arabic

5. Related words: bahsdosh(ot), bahslashmoq (fe'l)

Uzbek lexicography has achieved a number of achievements during the years of independence. After that, as a result, a five-volume “Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek language”, in 2012-2016, was created. New types of dictionaries, which the rich spiritual treasures, have been published, lexemes expressing our national values have received their true value, as well as computer linguistics has entered lexicography. However, much remains developing and improving Uzbek vocabulary. Uzbek lexicography still does not have a database of online dictionaries that work on the Internet. Therefore, the immediate application of the latest achievements of world linguistics in the Uzbek lexicography and its effective use in practice is one of the most important and urgent tasks.

In the “Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek language” the word “dictionary” is defined as follows:

Etymology: Arabic. (is derived from the words language, dialect, word, phrase)

Meaning: a set of words in a language and all words in a book and language are combined in a certain order (usually alphabetically), interpreted or translated into another language;²²

When it comes to a database, a source of data collection prioritizes its importance. In a traditional method of gathering, data can be compiled through a large number of paper dictionaries. This might be a time-consuming process, as a collector, first step to find related words and enter them into an electronic sheet. On the other hand, paper books cannot be updated as frequently as e-sources, combined data may become outdated in a short period of time.

The great deal of information in published dictionaries can be tapped by semi-automatic and full-automatic methods, to help build the computerized lexicons. Online consecutive processing of data using related periodicals can be considered another innovative way of data collection, which significantly decreases man-involved procedures and gathers up-to-date information. There are the number of online dictionaries in English while in Uzbek it does not exist. Cambridge.org, dictionary.com, merriam-webster.com, oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com, macmillandictionary.com, collinsdictionary.com and others are examples of English online dictionaries.

CONCLUSION

Most of the terminological dictionaries published so far exist a mixed or complex vocabulary in the form of encyclopedic, descriptive, mixed and mostly serve for educational purposes. However, the perfection of terminological systems and dictionaries of these systems largely relies on the scientific cooperation of specialists in several fields with linguists.

Incomplete or not, it is already becoming yesterday’s news with the frequent shift to electronic dictionaries. Some skills previously revealed in the context of paper dictionaries may still be of use in electronic dictionaries, such as the general cognitive skills of explaining lexicographic data, or selecting the right dictionary. Other paper dictionary skills and methods, for example the one having to do with locating inflected forms, are no longer needed in most modern electronic dictionaries, as new affordances make these older skills unnecessary. However, the introduction of new features themselves generates the demand for completely new skills, unfamiliar from paper products.

As mentioned above English dictionaries are developing and oneself can find out every type of them, paper, electronic and online, while in Uzbek paper as well as electronic dictionaries are available. Nowadays, it is rapid problem to create high-quality online dictionaries at the level of world standards, such as “Explanatory dictionary of Uzbek language”, “Etymological dictionary of Uzbek language”, “Morpheme dictionary of Uzbek language”, encyclopedic dictionaries, translation dictionaries; Explanatory dictionaries on different fields, “Dictionary of synonyms of the Uzbek language”, “Dictionary of antonyms of the Uzbek language”, “Dictionary of compound words”, and

²² Madvaliyev A., Mahkamov N., Mahmudov N. O ‘zbek tilining izohli lug ‘ati. – 2006. P.512

others. This, in turn, will take Uzbek computer lexicography to another level, inspiring new solutions to the issues.

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